

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE IN THE ACTIVITIES OF MEDICAL PERSONNEL

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada tibbiyot xodimlarining kasbiy faoliyatida psixologik bilimlarning ahamiyati ko'rib chiqiladi. Psixologiyani tibbiy amaliyotda qo'llashning asosiy jihatlari tahlil qilinadi. Davolash samaradorligini oshirish va bemorlar bilan o'zaro munosabatlarni yaxshilash uchun empatiya, muloqot qobiliyatlari va inson psixikasini tushunishning roli ta'kidlangan.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается важность психологических знаний в профессиональной деятельности медицинских работников. Анализируются основные аспекты применения психологии в медицинской практике. Подчеркивается роль эмпатии, коммуникативных навыков и понимания человеческой психики для повышения эффективности лечения и улучшения взаимодействия с пациентами.

Annotation. The article discusses the importance of psychological knowledge in the professional activities of medical professionals. The main aspects of the application of psychology in medical practice are analyzed. The role of empathy, communication skills and understanding of the human psyche is emphasized to increase the effectiveness of treatment and improve interaction with patients.

Kalit so'zlar: tibbiy psixologiya, kasbiy faoliyat, empatiya, muloqot

qobiliyatlari, bemor psixologiyasi.

Ключевые слова: медицинская психология, профессиональная деятельность, эмпатия, коммуникативные навыки, психология пациентов.

Keywords: medical psychology, professional activity, empathy, communication skills, psychology of patients.

Medical psychology is a component of general psychology that studies the role and importance of the psyche in the origin of diseases. Medical psychology, literally, is the science that studies patient psychology. But this definition does not cover all its possibilities, of course. Because he studies all the external and internal factors that cause the disease in healthy people and looks for their causes. Medical psychology is a comprehensive science, not knowing the limits. It has a long history, going through several periods in its development phase. The purpose of medical psychology is to find and approach the patient with methods that will undoubtedly have a therapeutic effect, taking into account his individual characteristics regarding his personality.

Medical psychology studies: 1) the psychic appearance of diseases. 2) what role the psyche plays in the origin and transition of diseases. 3) the role of the psyche in their treatment. 4) What role the psyche plays in the Prevention of diseases and strengthening of Health. The role of the psyche in the treatment of various diseases is huge, the importance of psychic influence on the sick in the treatment of the disease has already been proven. For the purpose of treatment for the sick, a routine psychic effect on the basis of a plan is called boorish psychotherapy. The role of the psyche in disease prevention health and strengthening is studied by the separate disciplines psychohygiene and psychoprophylaxis. Medical psychology includes 2 concepts that are close to each other, but differ from each other-psychopathology and pathophysiology (pathological psychology). Psychopathology it is, first of all, the total changes that

occur in the psyche in mental disorders, as well as in other diseases.

Medical practice includes not only the diagnosis and treatment of diseases, but also interaction with patients who require a high level of psychological competence. Modern medical specialists face patients of different ages, cultural and social groups, each of which has its own characteristics.

Statistics confirm the importance of the psychological component: according to a study by the World Health Organization (who, 2022), about 30% of cases of distrust of doctors are associated with ineffective communication. Additionally, 20% of patients do not follow prescribed treatment due to lack of confidence and inadequate emotional support.

They are seen, mainly in the following:

1. The importance of psychological knowledge in medical practice – psychological knowledge helps medical professionals solve several basic problems.

2. Establishing a reliable connection with the patient – communication patient complaints plays an important role in understanding, which helps to make an accurate diagnosis.

For example, a 2023 study in Europe found that active doctors who use listening have improved the diagnosis by 15 percent compared to those who ignore this approach.

– Understanding the emotional state of the patient. About 50% of patients are medical they are afraid of treatments. For example, patients who had given surgeons 5-10 minutes to discuss their concerns reported less postoperative stress.

- Prevention of professional fatigue. According to the World Health Organization (2023), more than 40% of medical workers experience symptoms of Occupational exhaustion. The introduction of regular training in psychology-based stress and emotional state management has reduced this figure by 18 percent in pilot medical institutions.

- The role of empathy and communication skills. Empathy interacts with the patient

the basis of the relationship. For example, empathic physicians can help increase patients ' commitment to treatment by up to 75%

For example, a patient with chronic back pain said that he changed three doctors until he found a specialist who not only prescribed treatment, but also listened to his emotional experiences. This approach helped the patient not only improve physical condition, but also restore psychological balance.

It should be said that effective communication skills include:

Active listening. For example, doctors who use the” paraphrasing ” method (repeating what the patient says in their own words) achieve mutual understanding 20% faster.

Supportive feedback. For example, phrases like “I understand how difficult this can be for you when treating cancer patients, but we work together to improve your condition” can help reduce anxiety levels by 30%.

Psychological approach in difficult situations. Medical practice is associated with situations that require psychological flexibility:

Work with incurable patients. Doctors who take psychological training courses are less likely to face the aggression or dissatisfaction of patients and their relatives.

Adventures. The introduction of mediation methods, for example, discussing situations with the participation of a psychologist, allows you to reduce the number of complaints in hospitals by 25 percent.

The influence of psychological knowledge on the results of treatment. Patients who feel emotional support recover faster. For example, according to some statistics, research data from cancer clinics in Moscow (2023) showed that patients receiving psychological assistance recorded an improvement in the general condition 1.5 times more.

A patient diagnosed with breast cancer should receive not only medical treatment, but also the help of a psychologist. This allowed him to tolerate chemotherapy more easily, as well as maintain a positive attitude, which, according to some experienced doctors, helped improve the prognosis.

Psychological knowledge is an important component of the professional qualifications of medical personnel. They help to improve the quality of medical care, build reliable relationships with patients and increase the personal stability of specialists.

Statistics and examples confirm that the introduction of psychological training into educational programs and practical activities of doctors has great potential to increase the effectiveness of modern medicine.

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